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ORIGINAL ARTICLE

CHALLENGES AND STRATEGIES FOR SUSTAINING NIGERIAN CHILDREN'S THEATRE IN THE COVID-19 ERA

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Abstract

The eruption of the Covid-19 pandemic across the globe and the resultant restrictions on social gathering has caused a lot of unforeseen problems which have continued to agitate the minds of many scholars in various disciplines. It is, therefore, not surprising at all that concerned scholars in Theatre and Media Studies have been concerned with the challenges posed to the existence of theatre in general and children's theatre in particular by the pandemic and the way forward. The present study is an effort in that direction, but it specifically turns attention to the neglected area of Nigerian children's theatre which has suffered a lot resulting from the lock-downs and clamp-downs on public theatres and parks for children's entertainment. Using insights from Albert Bandura's Social Learning Theory and Elihu Katz's Uses and Gratification Theory, the study makes a strong case for social entertainment as the way forward for sustaining and revitalising children's theatre in Nigeria in the Covid-19 era. It further recommends the government's intervention in providing constant power, subsidising the cost of data and providing befitting theatre for children's theatre programmes, among others.

Keywords: Challenges, Strategies, Sustaining, Nigerian, Children's, Theatre Covid-19, Era.

INTRODUCTION

Nothing in the recent history of the world has threatened the very existence of mankind and dislodged man's normal lifestyle more than the dreaded Covid-19 pandemic currently rampaging various parts of the world. There had indeed been gruesome world wars and violent crimes against humanity in various parts of the world at various times, coupled with biting economic hardship as well as outbreaks of life-threatening epidemics like LassaFever, the dengue disease, cholera, HIV/AIDS, and the like; but none, to the best of my knowledge, resulted in a global lockdown for several months like

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the Covid-19 pandemic which its second wave is still tormenting many parts of the world at the moment.

Suddenly shops, hotels, markets, schools and the ever-busy entertainment industries were shut down and human movements restricted to the barest minimum. Children to whom the play is an integral part of their everyday lives were forced to recoil inside their various houses as a part of the measures to curtail the spread of the dreaded disease. In Nigeria where children often congregate in any available space to engage in various forms of plays, the centre could no longer hold and things fell apart (to paraphrase Chinua Achebe). The few theatres and parks designated for children's entertainment mainly in the urban centres also went comatose. Although, some of the restrictions on public gathering have been lifted in Nigeria, the negative effects of covid-19 on children's theatre have remained very worrisome and challenging to parents, educationists and especially theatre experts because, as Peter Slade rightly observe: "Play is an inborn and vital part of young life. It is not an activity of idleness, but rather the child's way of thinking, proving, relaxing, working, remembering, daring, creating and absorbing" (1).

To him, therefore, play constitutes a significant aspect of children's lives. Uwem Okome avers in this regard that "Play is an important communication tool of the child and play is the work of every healthy child" (217). Katharine Anne Ommanney and Harry H. Schanker successfully capture the importance of play to humans from a general perspective when they write that:

Whether its setting has been the marble columns of ancient Greece, the crude carts of the Middle Ages, the cobbled inn yards of Elizabethan England, the glittering showboat on the Mississippi, the proscenium stages of the last 30 years, or the intimate, offbeat showplaces for our experimental theatre, the stage has always had a remarkable fascination for the average individual....(2).

With the above-identified crucial roles of plays in human lives in mind, especially in children's overall development, we can then easily imagine the sort of death-blow the Covid-19 pandemic and the consequent lockdowns have dealt on Nigerian children's theatre since the eruption of the disease and the restrictions on large gathering.

This paper is animated by that problem. It focuses on the challenges and strategies for sustaining and revitalising Nigerian children's theatre in the Covid-19 era, characterised by clampdowns on theatres, schools, churches, wedding receptions and other such places where children gather for plays. To achieve the aim of the paper, it will be fruitful to first throw some light on the meaning, features and importance of children's theatre before zeroing in on the challenges posed by Covid-19 and the strategies for sustaining and revitalising it. It is envisaged that this paper will contribute to the few numbers of existing literature in Nigerian children's theatre as well as broaden and enrich ideas on how to sustain Nigerian children's theatre amidst the Covid-19 challenges.

Children's Theatre, Meaning, Features and Importance

Most theatre scholars have their pet definitions of children's theatre with each emphasising some specific features and issues in children's theatre. Interestingly, Nkem Adichie captures the proliferating views on children's theatre when she asserts that "Children's theatre is a form of child drama that has been defined by many scholars in different ways" (84). To her, children's theatre is "a form of drama that involves adults, or adults and children performing for children" (84). This implies that it is not the age of the actors or actresses that matters, but the suitability of the content for the child audience. Faith Ibarakumo Ken-Aminikpo similarly asserts that children's theatre "has to do with theatre for children" (23). She did not get into the controversy of who constitutes the actors/actresses. For Goldberg, children's theatre is "a formal theatrical experience in which a play is presented for an audience of children" (5). Again, Goldberg seems not to be concerned with the age of the actors/actresses. To cite one more scholar, Osakue Stevenson Omoera proclaims that children's theatre is "an educational instructional approach which focuses on development through drama; it is a relaxed kind of theatre that is geared towards developing the participants" (210). Omoera's view suggests that children's theatre serves the purpose of edutainment: to entertain and at the same time to educate the young audience.

It is also noteworthy that some theatre scholars have come up with a taxonomy of children's theatre. Dennis Eluyela, for instance, has noted that there are three distinct forms of children's theatre, namely: "theatre with children", "theatre by children", and "theatre for children". According to him:

In theatre with children, children and adults are actors, working collaboratively to create a stimulating piece of performance. However, in theatre by children, children are the actors even though the devising and directing process might be done by adults. Adults, who are often professionals, are the actors in theatre for children (82).

Over the years, there have also been some misconceptions about children's theatre; one of the most notable of which is the common belief that children's theatre is "merely meant to please and entertain children", hence it does not require some serious attention and expertise like adult theatre. Far from this, however, children's theatre is not as simple or simplistic; and therefore calls for serious attention, perhaps even more than adult theatre, for it requires special subject matters, special themes, special techniques and special styles befitting its special child audience. For instance, children's drama should ideally not be too lengthy because children cannot watch and understand very long and convoluted episodes. The setting and props should also be specially designed to capture children's peculiar interests. Indeed, producers of children's theatre, therefore, need to carefully study children's psychology before going into production. They need to understand children's world and interests to be able to capture their attention.

Commenting on how to sustain children's interest in drama, Viola Spolin lays so much emphasis on the vital aspects of the environment and storyline

while producing children's theatre. According to her, "the child's physical environment should stimulate, excite and inspire play" (280). An ideal children's theatre environment should be spacious enough for various activities, like games, dance, props, costumes, lighting equipment, sound effects and also have enough space for the theatre audience. The storyline should be very interesting to attract and sustain children's interest.

In sum, a good children's play should be specifically and primarily created for children with storylines, plot, structure, themes, style and characters that are appealing and comprehensible to their young minds. Such plays should give room for improvisation and the participation of the children audience. While improvisation helps in building children's imaginative power, children's participation in the plays being acted for their enjoyment lures them to and sustains their interest in such plays. When children participate in singing, clapping, dancing, especially the ones that they are familiar with, they develop love and great interest in the plays.

Indeed, children's theatre plays significant roles in children's sound upbringing and should, therefore, be encouraged even amidst the Covid-19 and its resultant motley challenges. Matthew M. Umukoro succinctly and successfully articulate the functions and importance of children's theatre thus:

- i) *Impartation of knowledge*
- ii) *It encourages self-expression which leads to the self-discovery*
- iii) *It promotes self-awareness and diminishes negative self-consciousness*
- iv) *It develops the listening powers (as different from the natural hearing faculty) in the child.*
- v) *It sharpens the child's perception and capacity to observe minute details (as different from the natural use of the eyes)*
- vi) *It develops other human senses to the full for maximum effectiveness*
- vii) *It sharpens the child's power of imagination and concentration, resulting in specific forms of creativity based on individual talent.*
- viii) *It promotes and refines the powers of speech and effective communication*
- ix) *It facilitates social integration through group interaction and a sense of mutual understanding.*
- x) *It helps the child to cultivate the reading habit thus enhancing his or her capacity to source knowledge and information; and*
- xi) *It assists the child to develop into a full and rounded personality (13-14).*

These are, of course, in addition to the primary function of theatre: to entertain. William Shakespeare aptly captures the importance of pleasure (which theatre provides in quantum) in his famous assertion:

That man that hath no music in himself. Nor is not moved with concord of sweet sounds is fit for treasons, stratagems, and spoils; The motions of his spirit are dull as night and his affections dark as Erebus; let no such man be trusted (The Merchant of Venice, V. 1, 85).

Children's theatre, as we can see, contributes immensely to the development of children and society, for children are the leaders of tomorrow. There is, therefore, the need to sustain and revitalise Nigerian children's theatre which has been negatively affected by the outbreak of the Covid-19 Pandemic in Nigeria since 27th February 2020 when the case of the Pandemic was recorded in Nigeria till date.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Based on the already fact that children's theatre plays a significant role in children's overall development and that the media can be gainfully used to promote theatrical performances, this paper will be anchored on Albert Bandura's Social Learning Theory and Elihu Katz's Uses and Gratification Theory. In what follows, an attempt will be made to review the ideological stance of both theories to establish their appropriateness for this paper.

Albert Bandura's Social Learning Theory

Social learning theory is a theory propounded and popularised by Albert Bandura, an American-Canadian psychologist, at Stanford University in the year 1971. The theory stresses the fact that the mass media allow audience members to identify with any media character of their choice that demonstrates a behaviour that appeals to their minds and that they instinctively copy such behaviour. Nkem Adichie is of the view that "social learning theory is... one of the most famous and influential theories of learning in history" ("Content, Form and Socialisation" 19) because the theory is anchored on media effects on the audience. The theory postulates that the media have the potentials of shaping the audience's behaviours using observing other's behaviour. Stanley Baran further explains that "people model (copy) the behaviours they see and that modelling happens in two ways. The first is imitation, the direct replication, a special form of imitation in which observers do not copy exactly what they have seen but make a more generalised but related response" (425).

The idea of identification of models is of particular value to mass communication theorists who studied television's impact on behaviour. Therefore, one tread with caution on the type of television programme one must expose Nigerian children to so that they will not be negatively affected by the television contents/images bearing in mind their gullible and vulnerable nature, more especially now that entertainment is migrating to digital technology. More so, Katherine Miller (239) and Chioma Deborah Ekaeyemhe (46), add that the actors/actresses on television screens serve as role models (positively or negatively) for the audience who observe and imitate them. The relevance of this theory to the present study is that it promotes the use of social entertainment to inform and demonstrate how Nigerian children can cultivate good health habits such as wearing nose masks, washing of hands regularly, using hand sanitisers and maintaining social distancing. By watching young actors/actresses who display such actions, children will consciously and unconsciously imitate those actions, thereby observing the Covid-19 rules and contributing to winning the war

against the deadly pandemic.

Uses and Gratification Theory

The major postulation of this theory is that the media audience uses the media for many purposes: to acquire information, knowledge and understanding, to entertain, strengthen one's self-image and also to integrate and interact freely with others. Not until all these needs are met, the gratification of the audience is not yet met. Elihu Katz who propounded the Uses and Gratification Theory in 1970 is concerned with how people use the media for different purposes and to gratify their various needs. According to Stanley Baran, the uses and gratification theory "claimed that the media do not do things to people; rather, people do things with the media. In other words, the influence of the media is limited to what people allow it to be" (422). This implies that the audiences are the ones in need of the media content and then tune into media programmes of their choice to get their needs satisfied and not the other way round. The media are made in such a way that they satisfy the audience's needs and when these needs are satisfied, it has gratified the desired end.

Because the uses and gratification theory emphasises audience members' motives for making specific consumption choices and the consequences of that intentional media use, it is sometimes seen as being too apologetic for the media industries. In other words, when negative media effects are seen as the products of audience members' media choices and use, media industries are absolved of responsibility for the content they produce or carry. Meanwhile, the media simply give people what they want. Children, like their adult counterparts, seek their entertainment and education in the media and when their desire is met, it means it has gratified their needs. Likewise, the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) relies heavily on the media to inform, educate and enlighten the public on the causes, symptoms and preventive measures of the deadly disease, coronavirus. When the aim is achieved, it has gratified the desired end. Like Bandura's Social Learning Theory, Katz's Uses and Gratification Theory emphasises the role of the media in educating children. These theories provide the framework for this paper which seeks to highlight the challenges and strategies for sustaining Nigerian children's theatre in the Covid-19 era.

Challenges Facing the Sustenance of Nigerian Children's Theatre in the Covid-19 Era

As earlier hinted, the eruption of the Covid-19 pandemic and the prolonged lockdown and subsequent clampdown on formal theatrical performances in Nigeria have further deepened the challenges facing the development of children's theatre in the country. Before now, concerned theatre aficionados and scholars had lamented over the poor attention given to children's theatre by the successive governments in Nigeria which evince in the existence of few theatres specifically designed for children, poor funding, lack of experts in the area of children's theatre and low patronage of children's theatre

performances, among others. The neglect of children's theatre in Nigeria is further evidenced in the lack of interest in the area among theatre scholars. For instance, no scholar among the contributors to Yemi Ogunbiyi's authoritative book on Nigerian Theatre: *Drama and Theatre in Nigeria: A Critical Source Book*, 1981 commented on children's theatre. This ugly situation has been worsened by the eruption of the Covid-19 pandemic in Nigeria in February 2020 leading to the closure of the few children's theatres in the country. In what follows, therefore, we will attempt to identify some of the major challenges the outbreak of Covid-19 has posed to the existence and development of Nigerian children's theatre.

i) Lockdown and Closure of Theatres in Nigeria

As a part of the measures to control the spread of Covid-19, the Federal Government of Nigeria, like its counterparts across the globe, imposed lockdowns that not only restricted people's movements but also forced theatres, schools, event places and other places where children engage in plays to close down. The effect of this on children's theatre is that neither the actors and actresses nor the patronising audience can engage in children's theatre as they used to do before the outbreak of the covid-19 pandemic.

ii) Fear of Contacting the Dreaded Virus

Apart from being compelled by the government to stay at home, many people have also developed a phobia for visiting public places, like theatres, for fear of contacting Covid-19. This has affected rehearsals, production and patronage of Nigerian children's theatre.

iii) Economic Hardship

The prolonged lockdowns have negative effects on people's sources of income. For instance, some traders whose shops have remained closed for months cannot indulge in the luxury of taking their children to theatres anymore even if they adhere to the Covid-19 guidelines. The same applies to some parents who work in private schools and other establishments whose salaries are either slashed or stopped. Normally, people tend to grapple with the basic problems of feeding, clothing and housing before going for pleasure. This researcher's interaction with some workers at the Port Harcourt Treasure Park and Nigerian Television Authority (N.T.A) Port Harcourt reveals that most of the children who used to flood into their premises for children's entertainment programmes suddenly stopped coming. Those workers traced this to the drop in parents' earnings as a result of Covid-19 and its resultant lockdowns.

iv) Lack of Modern Theatres Specifically Designed for Children

It is a fact that Nigeria lacks modern theatres essentially designed for children. Children naturally like spacious environments with assorted playing equipment which, unfortunately, Nigeria at the moment does not have. Most of the few existing theatres in the country lack adequate space and enough ventilation ideal for a large number of children. Such theatres are certainly not in sync with the policy of social distancing which the

World Health Organisation and the Nigerian Centre for Disease Control recommend as one of the measures for combating Covid-19.

v) **Lack of Adequate Personal Protective Equipment for Both the Performers and the Audience**

There is a dearth of personal protective equipment like face masks, sanitisers and handwashing buckets in public places in Nigeria. This situation makes it extremely difficult for people, especially children to freely visit theatres to patronise theatrical performances.

vi) **Lack of the Materials Necessary for Electronic-Entertainment**

Many Nigerians are poor and cannot afford televisions, videos, and smart cell phones needed for E-entertainment also called social entertainment. Wikipedia defines social entertainment as “an online service, platform or website which links back to social networking websites to help connect users and has begun to facilitate audience acquisition” (web).

Even among the few children whose parents can afford such gadgets, many still face the challenge of not having access to constant electric power and poor connection to the network. But despite all these challenges, Nigerian children's theatre still has some prospects and can be sustained if the following appropriate measures are taken.

Strategies for Sustaining Nigerian Children's Theatre amidst Covid-19

The major strategy for sustaining Nigerian children's theatre in the Covid-19 era is for Nigerian children to join the rest of the world and embrace social entertainment which takes care of the problem of lockdowns and the challenge of observing social distancing. Social entertainment as earlier noted involves the use of online concerts, e-games, movies and animations. Lesley Luk effectively captures the rising popularity of social entertainment following the outbreak of Covid-19 thus:

The Media and Entertainment (M&E) sector has seemingly moved swiftly in response to Covid-19 by producing online concerts virtually, ramping up e-gaming, offering free entertainment subscriptions (i.e. communication companies have offered free access to a rotating selection of channels), releasing big blockbuster movies directly online, and animation studios adopting a fully remote working environment.... (“Foreword”).

Mark Hanson similarly proclaims that the future of children's entertainment lies in social entertainment. He further asserts that “while I can't predict the future, I do know that when audiences return, the pandemic's legacy will likely be that it accelerated the arts ability to connect with audiences through technology” (Web n.p).

However, it is also worth stating that social entertainment can have some negative effects on the young and vulnerable audience, especially the Nigerian child if they are not carefully monitored. One of such negative effects is that

social entertainment does not encourage group interaction which conventional theatre via physical contact promotes. It, thus, does not promote physical socialisation. According to UNICEF, "Smartphones are fuelling a bedroom culture with online access for many children becoming more personal, more private and less supervised" (1). It further explains that online entertainment poses "significant risks to children's safety, privacy and well-being, magnifying threats and harms that many children already face offline and making already – vulnerable children even more vulnerable" (8).

In sum, then, for social entertainment to successfully fill the void caused by the outbreak of Covid-19 in Nigerian children's theatre, parents and guardians should help to monitor and control what their children watch online. Hence the media have some pragmatic effects on the audience, children should be encouraged to patronise programmes that will positively influence them. For Nigerian children, in particular, there is the danger of them being exposed to unwholesome movies that do not promote the good aspects of Nigerian and African cultural heritage. This is so because most of the available programmes in social media were not specifically designed for the local audience. In the light of the grave danger inherent in allowing Nigerian children to gulp exotic programmes that may be filled with corruptive scenes, it is advised that Nigerian theatre experts should domesticate the social entertainment programmes for the consumption and general well-being of the Nigerian child. As Ilami Krama has rightly advised in this regard:

It is vital to note that Nigerian drama must be culturally relative to reinforce the traditional worldview or the native schema that has sustained our traditional societies. It is also imperative for the drama to mediate in the development of core values related to the growth of the individual, society and institutions. The values reinforced should be derived from the core traditional values and not from the prevailing social conditions (337).

Ifeyinwa Uzundu reinforces the point by asserting that:

When children watch movies with violent themes, they develop tendencies for criminal acts like bullying, kicking, raping and other delinquent behaviours. When they watch amorous scenes, they have the likelihood of developing sexual orgies or stimulation for sexual escapades. In movies where their so-called "Models" flaunt their cleavages and other sensitive parts, they learn to dress half-naked parading all corners and streets with them... In the same vein, when children listen to foul language or vulgarity... they equally learn to be immodest in their choices of words (63).

The obvious implication of all these is that Nigerian theatre experts should not only go digital but should also dig deep into the sub-soil of Nigerian socio-cultural heritage and produce entertainment programmes that are at once interesting, morally edifying and strongly rooted in the core Nigerian values such as respect for elders, friendliness, hospitality, resourcefulness, love for one's

neighbours and honesty, among many others.

Furthermore, the contents of such programmes can be fruitfully used in demonstrating how children can help in conquering the Covid-19 pandemic through proper and regular washing of hands, wearing of face masks, using sanitisers and avoiding handshaking. Nigerian children's theatre can also be used to stress the importance of observing social distancing. For maximum effects, some of such programmes can be presented in indigenous Nigerian languages or the popular Nigerian Pidgin to reach out to a larger audience.

To enhance the effective use of the social entertainment approach to propagate children's theatre in Nigeria in the Covid-19 era, the government can also help to subsidise the high cost of phones and data to enable children from poor homes to benefit from online entertainment. At present, most of the children in the rural areas seem to be virtually cut off from the little gains being made from social entertainment platforms.

In addition, children should be taught some basic computer skills to enable some who do not yet know how to use online facilities to learn them. This can be achieved by introducing computer appreciation in the Nigerian primary and secondary school system when normal academic activities resume across the states.

Finally, the government should formulate and implement economic policies that will improve the economic well-being of Nigerians. It is only when people have enough money to eat, clothe and shelter themselves that they can fully patronise children's theatre in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

This paper has attempted to highlight some of the challenges and strategies for sustaining Nigeria's children's theatre in the Covid-19 era. The study revealed that the outbreak of the dreaded Covid-19 Pandemic in Nigeria has had several negative effects on the sustenance and development of Nigeria's children's theatre. Such challenges include the lockdown and the subsequent shut down of theatres in Nigeria; the growing fear of contracting the disease among theatre lovers; the harsh economic situation in the country which has been worsened by the lockdown, the absence of modern theatres specifically designed for the Nigerian child; and lack of basic personal protective equipment for the child actors/actress; their trainers and the audience.

As for the strategies, the paper hinged the hope of sustaining and revitalising Nigeria's children theatre in the Covid-19 era on the use of social entertainment because of its wide outreach and conformity to the World Health Organisation's recommendations on how to eradicate the pandemic, notably by maintaining social distancing. The paper, however, observed that social entertainment can only be gainfully used if parents effectively monitor the content of the programmes their children watch. It further suggested that for social media to serve its function in sustaining Nigerian children's theatre, Nigerian theatre experts should strive to create programmes that promote virtue and African

socio-cultural values rather than exposing children to some corruptive foreign programmes. Furthermore, the paper recommended that such programmes should be better if they are presented in Nigeria's major indigenous languages and Pidgin to reach out to more children who may not have a good understanding of the English Language.

Finally, the paper called on the government to revitalise the economy, subsidise the cost of phones and data, build modern theatres that have the necessary facilities for children's entertainment as well as provide adequate personal protective equipment for children theatre practitioners, their trainers and the audience. The researcher strongly believes that if these measures are carefully implemented, they will help to cushion the negative effects of the covid-19 Pandemic on Nigerian children's theatre which plays a crucial role in the proper upbringing of the Nigerian child.

REFERENCES

- Adichie, Nkem Godslove.** "Challenges of Sustaining the Child's Interest in Uniport Children's Theatre". In *International Journal of Research, Innovation & Development*. 2013. Pp. 81-88.
-"Content, Form and Socialisation in Selected Children's Television Dramas in Nigeria". Unpublished PhD. Thesis. Department of Theatre and Film Studies, University of Port Harcourt. 2019.
- Bran, Stanley.** *Introduction to Mass Communication*. 5th ed. Mc Graw-Hill Higher Education. 2009.
- Ekaeyemhe, Deborah Chioma.** "The Impact of Television Viewing on Nigerian Cultural Norms and Values: Analysis of Some Primetime Television Stations". Unpublished M.A. Dissertation. Department of Theatre Arts, University of Port Harcourt. 2004.
- Eluyefa, Dennis.** "Children's Theatre: A Brief Pedagogical Approach". In *Artspraxis*. Vol. 4. No.1. 2017. pp: 79-83.
- Goldberg, M.** *Children's Theatre: A Philosophy and a Method*. Englewood Cliff. 1974.
- Harson, Mark C.** "The Day the Music Died". In Audrey Azoulay, Rahul Bhatia, Rick Cordella, Mark C. Harson, Battasor Kormakur, Jonathan Kuntz, David Clay Large and James S. Snyder (eds.). *Culture Shock: Eight Voices on the Future of Entertainment, Culture and Sports*. <https://foreignpolicy.com/2020/08/15/covid-19-pandemic-culture-sports-entertainment/2020>.
- Ken-Aminikpo, Faith Ibarakumo.** *Theatre and Drama in Education*. Oscom Prints. 2017.
- Krama, Ilami Clive.** "Henry Bell-Gam's *Hidden Treasure* and Social Limits of Nigerian Drama". In Onyemaechi Udumukwu. (ed.). *Nigerian Literature in English: Emerging Critical Perspectives*. M&J. Grand Orbit

- Communications.2007. Pp. 326-338.
- Luk, Lesley.** *What Covid-19 Means for the Media and Entertainment Industry: A Look at the Canadian Landscape.* <https://home.kpmg/ca/en/home/contacts//lesley-luk/html/>. 2020.
- Miller, M.** *Communication Theories: Perspectives, Processes and Contexts.*Texas: Mc Graw-Hill. 2002.
- Ommanney, Katharine Anne & Harry H. Schanker.** *The Stage & the School.*5th ed. Mc. Graw-Hill Book Company. 1982.
- Omoera, Osakue Stevenson.** “Repositioning Early Childhood Education in Nigeria: The Children’s Theatre Approach”. In *Academic Research International*. Vol. 1. No. 2. 2011. Pp. 206-214.
- Shakespeare, William.** *The Merchant of Venice.*Pearson Education. 1962.
- Slade, Peter.** *An Introduction to Child Drama.*University of London Press. 1958.
- Spolin, Viola.** *Improvisation for the Theatre.*Illinois Northwestern University, Press,1963.
- Umukoro, M. Matthew.** *Drama and Theatre in Nigerian Schools: A Blueprint of Educational Drama and Theatre.*Caltop Publications, 2002.
- UNICEF.** *Children in a Digital World.*Retrieved from <https://reliefweb.int/.../world/state-worlds-children-2017-children-digital-world-enar>.Accessed on the 27thSeptember 2020.
- Uwem, Okome.** “Developing the Acting Spirit in Children Through Educational Drama” in Effiong Johnson (ed.). *The Art of Acting: A Student Friendly Anthology.* 2005.
- Uzundu, Ifeyinwa** “Pornography, Mass Media and Youth Socialisation in Nigeria.*Benue Journal of Youth and Development.* Maiden Edition, 2015. Pp.57-68.

